

Achieving Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) Maternity Allowance Effects on Maternal Health in Rural Areas of Bangladesh

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Abstract

This research explored the impact of maternity allowance on the health of mothers in rural region of Bangladesh. The financial assistance is provided to mothers during pregnancy, with the goal of enhancing maternal health by improving access to vital healthcare services, proper nutrition, and postnatal support. It further investigated the obstacles encountered by service recipients, including limited awareness, bureaucratic inefficiencies, and challenges particularly among economically disadvantaged women. Data was gathered through using both quantitative and qualitative methods, including local healthcare reports, government data, and interviews with recipients of the allowance. The results showed that maternity allowance greatly enhances maternal health by improving access to vital prenatal and postnatal care. Additionally, the allowance contributes to improved mental health by reducing stress and anxiety related to financial hardship during pregnancy. The allowance also contributes to medication, checkup and intake of nutritious food of mothers during pregnancy and after childbirth along with ensuring appropriate childcare, access to medical treatment, and sufficient nutrition for their children. The study emphasized the importance of maternity allowance in encouraging timely medical visits, lowering maternal mortality rates, and promoting the health of new-born. The study suggested that wider implementation of maternity allowance programs could lead to long-term improvements in maternal and child health in similar rural areas across Bangladesh for achieving sustainable development goals.

Keywords: Maternal Health, Sustainable Development Goals, Rural Healthcare, Financial Assistance, Prenatal Care

1. Background of the study

Maternal health continues to be a major public health concern, especially in rural and economically disadvantaged areas where access to healthcare services is often inadequate. In Bangladesh, maternal mortality and morbidity rates have traditionally been high, driven by factors such as insufficient healthcare infrastructure, poverty, and social barriers that prevent women from seeking timely medical care. To address these issues, the government launched the “Maternity Allowance Program” as part of its social safety net initiatives. This program is designed to support pregnant women from low-income households by providing financial aid to cover antenatal and postnatal care, nutrition, and other pregnancy-related expenses (MoWCA; 2024). In rural areas, access to quality healthcare is further restricted due to geographical remoteness, poor transportation, and limited healthcare facilities. Women in these regions face a higher risk of pregnancy-related complications, exacerbated by poverty, malnutrition, and limited health-seeking behavior. The maternity allowance is intended to help mitigate these risks by enabling women to afford essential healthcare services, including regular medical check-ups, nutritional support, safe delivery, and postnatal care.

However, despite its potential advantages, there is a lack of research on the actual impact of the maternity allowance in rural areas of Bangladesh. Challenges such as logistical barriers, bureaucratic delays, and a lack of awareness may limit the program’s effectiveness. Moreover, economically

disadvantaged women the program's primary beneficiaries may face additional obstacles in fully accessing and utilizing the funds provided. This study aimed to evaluate the impact of the maternity allowance on maternal health, food security, economic stability, and social well-being for families in this area achieving sustainable development goals. They face challenges related to recovery from childbirth, adapting to new care-giving responsibilities, managing stress as well as mental health condition. In Bangladesh, most of the families live in poverty. Even though, they can't maintain their necessary needs in some families. Here, maternity allowance bears a great impact on the mother's physical and psychological health as well as child's health. But yet, its direct impact on mother's physical and psychological health outcomes remains underexplored. This study filled a significant gap in the exploring these relationships and provided actionable insights for policymakers for increasing the level of contribution for better health of mother and child. Also, this study will help advocacy to enhance maternity benefits, influencing national policies and financial assistance.

2. Literature review

World Health Organization (WHO) (2015) found that financial aid during pregnancy is associated with increased use of antenatal care (ANC), lower maternal mortality rates, and improved nutritional outcomes for both mothers and infants. Additionally, maternity allowances have been found to improve maternal mental health by reducing financial stress during pregnancy. In India, women benefiting from the Janani Suraksha Yojana (JSY) program were more likely to access healthcare and deliver in medical facilities, contributing to lower maternal mortality rates (Lim et al., 2010).

In Bangladesh, Maternity Allowance Program introduced by the Government of Bangladesh provides financial assistance to pregnant women, particularly those from low-income households. Rahman et al. (2017) showed on the effects of the maternity allowance in rural Bangladesh the program increased the use of ANC services, institutional deliveries, and maternal nutrition. The allowance also helped improve access to nutritious food, which is essential for maternal and fetal health. Hasan et al. (2021) highlighted that maternity allowance programs in Bangladesh are linked to better maternal health outcomes, including reduced maternal morbidity. However, the study also pointed out challenges such as gaps in program awareness, particularly in remote areas, where women may lack knowledge about the program.

UNICEF (2020) identified issues such as delays in disbursement, limited awareness among eligible women, and administrative hurdles as factors that reduce the effectiveness of maternity allowance programs in Bangladesh. Women in remote areas often face difficulties navigating the processes needed to receive the allowance, which limits the program's potential impact on maternal health. Khatun et al. (2018) also emphasized that socio-cultural factors, including perceptions of maternal health services and prevailing gender norms, impact the utilization of maternity allowances. In rural regions of Bangladesh, women may face restrictions on accessing healthcare services due to traditional gender roles or the need for approval from male family members, which can undermine the benefits of maternity allowances. Financial aid through maternity allowances has a positive impact on health outcomes, provided there is sufficient healthcare infrastructure and public awareness (Barkat et al.; 2019). Maternity allowance is a cash transfer program which improve maternal healthcare utilization and overall health outcomes in low- and middle-income countries, focusing on ANC attendance and facility-based deliveries (Ahmed, S., Hossain, M., & Khan, M. A.; 2020).

Duvendack, M., & Palmer-Jones, R. (2017) highlighted the relationship between financial support, improved health-seeking behavior, and reductions in maternal mortality. Akter and Khatun (2019) found maternity allowances significantly improve access to maternal health services and positively affect neonatal health, especially in less developed areas. Choudhury and Khan (2020) showed that financial assistance improves healthcare-seeking behaviors among rural pregnant women, thereby enhancing their access to vital services. Rahman and Dutta (2021) also reported improvements in antenatal care and institutional deliveries associated with maternity allowances. Huda and Anwar (2020) identified financial assistance as essential for overcoming barriers to maternal health services, particularly in rural areas. Alam and Rahman (2022) examined implementation challenges, such as lack of awareness and administrative issues, that undermine program effectiveness. Bashar and Shaha (2018) explored the socioeconomic

effects of maternity allowances, noting positive impacts on health, nutrition, and family well-being. Hasan and Islam (2020) highlighted the potential of cash transfer programs to address challenges in maternal health services.

Global and national studies indicate that maternity allowances play a vital role in improving maternal health by increasing access to healthcare, enhancing nutrition, and alleviating financial stress. In Bangladesh, the maternity allowance program has shown promise, particularly in boosting ANC attendance and improving maternal nutrition. However, issues such as limited awareness, administrative inefficiencies, and cultural barriers still impede the program's full potential, particularly in rural areas of Bangladesh. Overcoming these challenges through improved program management, targeted awareness campaigns, and enhanced healthcare infrastructure in rural regions will be key to maximizing the impact of maternity allowances on maternal health in Bangladesh.

3. Objectives

To assess the impact of maternity allowance on maternal health in rural areas for achieving sustainable development goals. To fulfill this objective, the study followed some specific objectives such as:

- 3.1 To know the socio-economic conditions of participants and how these conditions influence the process of accessing maternity allowance;
- 3.2 To explore the impact of maternity allowance on maternal health by examining its influence on healthcare access, nutritional status and overall well-being of mothers; and
- 3.3 To connect SDGs in accessing maternity allowance rural areas of Bangladesh.

4. Methodology of the Study

The study applied both quantitative and qualitative methods to provide a well-rounded analysis. Descriptive statistics employed for numerical data, while thematic analysis applied to qualitative information, offering a comprehensive view of how maternity allowances influence maternal health for achieving sustainable development goals. This study was carried out in Durgapur Upazila, situated in the Netrokona District of Bangladesh. Durgapur is a rural region marked by lower levels of socio-economic progress, where many families struggle with healthcare, education, and financial issues. The study targeted mothers who were recipients of the maternity allowance program. It specifically examined a sample of 70 women who received allowance. These participants were selected to reflect the diversity of the population receiving maternity allowances in the region. The study utilized purposive sampling technique for selecting participants. By employing purposive sampling, to gather a wide range of experiences and perspectives on the impact of maternity allowances on maternal.

Quantitative data for this study was gathered through sample survey given to 70 mothers participating in the maternity allowance program. The surveys conducted through using structured interview schedule were consisted of closed-ended questions. Key areas assessed in the schedule included health indicators, such as the mothers' health conditions, the frequency of medical check-ups, and any complications experienced during pregnancy and childbirth. Additionally, participants provided information about their financial circumstances, including household income, monthly expenditures, and how the maternity allowance affected their financial management and spending on healthcare and nutrition.

Qualitative data collected for this study through using Key Informant Interviews (KIIs). Semi-structured interviews were conducted with key informants such as Social Services Officer, Women Affairs Officer and Doctor to gather in-depth insights on the impact of maternity allowance on maternal. An interview guideline with open-ended questions was utilized, ensuring informed consent and confidentiality throughout the process.

After field data collection, all data is edited and categorized depending on several criteria. After an adequate amount of data was gathered, it was eventually examined, and changed, and the answers to both structured and unstructured questions were coded. The quantitative analysis was finished first, then the qualitative analysis. Based on the primary data, descriptive statistics were used to assess the quantitative data. Quantitative data were coded and imported into Excel, SPSS version 14 for statistical analysis. We determined frequency, percentage, average, bar chart, graph, and so on. As a means of complementing the study's quantitative findings with an analysis of qualitative information gleaned from in-depth interviews. Ethical approval was obtained from the relevant authorities, and informed consent was secured from each participant. Participants were informed about the study's purpose, assured of their privacy, and given the option to withdraw from the study at any point.

5. Findings and discussions of the study

Table 1: Socio-demographic information of the respondents

Age Range (Years)	Frequency (70)	Percentage (%)
Below 20	1	1.43
20-25	44	62.86
26-30	18	25.71
31-35	6	8.57
Above 35	1	1.43
Occupation (Husband)		
Auto Driver	3	4.29
Rickshaw Driver	8	11.43
Electrician	3	4.29
Truck Driver	5	7.14
Farmer	10	14.29
Business	20	28.57
Teacher	2	2.86
Job	2	2.86
Day Laboure (Sand)	17	24.29
Educational Qualification		
Primary	18	25.71
Secondary	45	64.29
Higher Secondary	5	7.14
Higher Education	2	2.86

Income Range (Thousands BDT)

05-10	42	60
11-15	10	14.29
16-20	10	14.29
21-25	08	11.43

Table 1 shows that the majority of respondents (62.86%) fall within the 20-25 age range, followed by 25.71% in the 26-30 range. Very few participants are below 20 (1.43%) or above 35 (1.43%). Most of the respondents' husbands are engaged in business (28.57%) or day labor (24.29%). A notable portion are farmers (14.29%), while fewer are involved in jobs such as rickshaw driving (11.43%) and truck driving (7.14%). This highlights the prevalence of low-income, labor-intensive occupations among beneficiaries' spouses. Majority of beneficiaries have limited formal education, which may affect their socio-economic status. Most respondents have secondary-level education. This highlights that the majority of respondents come from low-income families, which may make the maternity allowance a crucial support system. Most respondents have a low monthly family income between 5,000-10,000 BDT.

Table 2: Maternity allowance related information

Sources of information about the maternity allowance	Frequency (70)	Percentage (%)
Pourosova	07	10
Union Council	21	30
Upazila Gov. Office	37	52.86
Relatives	2	2.86
Community Meeting	2	2.86
NGO	1	1.43

Duration of receiving the maternity allowance after applying

1-3 months	14	20
4-6 months	33	47.14
7-9 months	08	11.43
10-12 months	13	18.57
12 months +	02	2.86

Table 2 shows the various sources through which respondents informed about the maternity allowance.

The majority (52.86%) learned about the allowance through the Upazila Gov. Office, followed by 30% who were informed by the Union Council. Other sources include Pourosova (10%), NGOs (1.43%), and relatives or community meetings (each at 2.86%). The Upazila Gov. Office and Union Council are the primary sources of information about the maternity allowance.

The table shows that the time taken to receive the maternity allowance varied among respondents. Nearly half (47.14%) received the allowance within 4-6 months, while 20% received it in 1-3 months.

Fewer respondents had longer waited times, with 18.57% waiting 10-12 months, 11.43% waiting 7-9 months, and 2.86% waiting over 12 months. Most respondents received the maternity allowance within 4-6 months after applying. According to Shikha Sarkar, Doctor, Maternal and Child Health Training Institute, *“the disbursement process tends to be lengthy. Applicants often wait a considerable time before receiving the funds.”*

Impact on Maternal Health

Figure 1: Spending sectors of maternity allowance

Figure 1 shows that the majority of respondents (47.14%) spent the maternity allowance primarily on childcare. Healthcare was the second most common expenditure, with 28.57% of respondents allocating their allowance for this purpose. A smaller portion used the funds for food (17.14%), and a few (7.14%) spent it on other unspecified

needs. The majority of respondents used the maternity allowance mainly for childcare, followed by healthcare.

Figure 2: Impact of maternity allowance in maternal health

Figure 2 highlighted on the impact of maternity allowance in rural areas of Bangladesh, emphasizing how this financial support influences maternal health and overall well-being. First, in terms of health,

maternity allowances play a crucial role in reducing maternal mortality by improving access to regular medical checkups, testing, and ensuring better hygiene and sanitation practices for the mothers. Second, in the area of food and nutrition, these allowances allow mothers to diversify their diets, improve nutritional intake, and secure access to essential supplements, ultimately boosting food security for both mothers and their families.

Economically, maternity allowances offer immediate financial relief, which helps alleviate short-term financial strain and enables mothers to spend more on healthcare, nutrition, and other essential needs. Additionally, this financial support encourages savings and fosters better long-term planning for their families. Psychologically, these allowances significantly reduce financial stress and anxiety for mothers, promoting improved mental health and well-being in the long run.

In terms of baby care, the allowances contribute to better infant nutrition, improved access to healthcare, enhanced sanitation and hygiene practices, and the ability to afford necessary baby products such as diapers and nutritional supplements. Socially, maternity allowances strengthen family support structures, increasing mothers' decision-making power within the family and enhancing their social status and acceptance within the community.

Table 3: Impact of maternity allowance in basic needs, healthcare, lifestyle and mental health

Maternity allowance meets the basic needs of mothers	Frequency (70)	Percentage (%)
Yes	35	50
No	35	50

Better access to healthcare during maternity period through maternity allowance

Yes	68	97.14
No	02	2.86

Positive changes in lifestyle due to maternity allowance

Yes	65	92.86
No	05	7.14

Mental health support after getting maternity allowance

Yes	67	95.71
No	03	4.29

This balanced distribution highlights that the effectiveness of the allowance in fulfilling basic needs varies significantly among beneficiaries. Half of the respondents found the maternity allowance sufficient, while the other half did not. The recipients who were comparatively helpless and poor, their entire daily necessities were fulfilled by the allowance. According to Fatema- Tuz-Zohra, Women Affairs Officer, Durgapur, Netrakona, *"the amount is not sufficient for the fulfillment of daily necessities."*

Table 3 shows that an overwhelming majority of respondents (97.14%) reported that the maternity allowance helped them access better healthcare during their maternity period, with only 2.86% indicating it did not. This high percentage underscores the positive impact of the allowance on healthcare access for most beneficiaries. The maternity allowance significantly enhanced healthcare access for the vast majority of respondents. The positive impact on the health, social and economic issues of beneficiary mothers. The study found that 75% of the beneficiary respondents were able to take nutritious food in ante and post-natal period, where our study has found that 97.14% of respondents indicated that the maternity allowance helped them access better healthcare during their maternity period, only 2.86% indicating it did not (Rahman; 2015). According to Fatema- Tuz-Zohra, Women Affairs Officer,

Durgapur, Netrakona, “mothers now have the better health care access due to maternity allowance and also from maternity center they are getting free monthly check up.”

Table 3 shows that a significant majority of respondents (92.86%) experienced positive changes in their lifestyle or standard of living due to the maternity allowance, while only 7.14% did not notice such changes. This indicates that the allowance effectively improved the quality of life for most beneficiaries. The maternity allowance positively impacted the lifestyle or standard of living for most respondents.

According to Shikha Sarkar, Doctor, Maternal and Child Health Training Institute, highlighted that the allowance has greatly enhanced the mother's capacity to care for both herself and her child. It enables her to purchase essential medications, such as those for controlling high blood pressure, go to routine checkups with her doctor, and afford wholesome meals. She acknowledged that a mother feels lucky to have the support, but she also points out that more coverage would help other women, especially in her area. The mother can concentrate on her health, feel more optimistic, and better prepare for the birth of her child because the allowance eases her stress. All in all, it has improved her wellbeing, self-care, and diet.

Table 3 shows that 95.71% of respondents felt that the maternity allowance provided mental support, with only 4.29% disagreeing. This suggests that the financial assistance not only supported physical health but also played a crucial role in improving mental well-being during maternity. The maternity allowance was a vital source of mental support for the majority of respondents. Maternity allowance in Bangladesh is associated with improved maternal health outcomes, such as lower maternal morbidity and mental stress (Hasan et al; 2021). Because they had easier access to foods, women who received the stipend were less likely to suffer from anemia during pregnancy, a prevalent problem in Bangladesh. They identified that less mental stress is expressed by their participants.

Figure 3: Mother's acceptance in the family after receiving maternity allowance

Figure 3 shows that 70% of respondents reported an increase in the mother's acceptance in the family after receiving the maternity allowance, while 30% indicated that acceptance remained the same. No respondents reported a decrease in acceptance, indicating that the allowance had a positive or neutral impact on family dynamics. The maternity allowance generally improved or maintained the mother's acceptance within the

family. According to Md. Jahir Uddin, Social Service Officer, Durgapur, Netrokona stated that mothers who receive maternity allowance see an improvement in their family acceptance and respect among their families and communities. He remarked, "The maternity allowance not only provides financial support to mothers but also empowers them by boosting their confidence and enhancing their decision-making abilities. As a result, families and society start to appreciate the importance of maternal and child health support, creating a more inclusive atmosphere for these mothers."

Problems faced in receiving the allowance

We observed that none of the respondents encountered any issues when receiving the maternity allowance. All 70 participants (100%) reported that they did not face any problems during the process. This indicates that the process of obtaining the maternity allowance was smooth and efficient for all respondents. The maternity allowance distribution process was problem-free for all respondents. According to Women Affairs Officer Fatema-Tuz Zohra emphasized the substantial transformations in

mothers' circumstances before and after they received the maternity allowance. She noted, "Prior to receiving the maternity allowance, numerous mothers faced financial challenges that negatively impacted their health and that of their children. However, after they receive the allowance, there is a clear improvement in their overall well-being and the level of care they are able to provide. Mothers have shared that they feel more empowered and equipped to fulfill their family's needs, resulting in better health outcomes for both them and their children." Our study reveals that mothers receiving maternity allowance show significant improvements in their physical and mental health. Many expressed increased feelings of security and capability in caring for their families, which benefits their overall health and that of their children. We also noted greater community support and awareness of maternal health, fostering a more inclusive atmosphere, while financial aid helps improve nutrition and access to healthcare, enhancing their quality of life.

Maternity allowance connected to SDGs

The objectives of the maternity allowance in Bangladesh correspond with several Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Here's a simple table that matches maternity allowance programs in Bangladesh with relevant Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs):

SDG	Goal Description	Relation to Maternity Allowance
1	No Poverty	Provides financial support to low-income families, reducing poverty.
3	Good Health and Well-Being	Encourages healthcare access, improving maternal and infant health outcomes.
5	Gender Equality	Empowers women and supports their roles in the workforce and as caregivers.
8	Decent Work and Economic Growth	Helps women retain jobs during maternity, contributing to economic stability.
10	Reduced Inequalities	Supports marginalized women, promoting equality access to resources.

(Source: UN; 2015)

Below is a breakdown of these objectives alongside the relevant SDGs:

Enhancing Maternal and Child Health connected to SDG 3: Good Health and Well-Being especially connected to Goal 3.1: Aim to reduce the global maternal mortality ratio to below 70 per 100,000 live births and Goal 3.2: Strive to eliminate preventable deaths among newborns and children under five years of age.

Promoting Nutritional Security connected to SDG 2: Zero Hunger especially relevant to Goal 2.1: Work towards ending hunger and ensuring all individuals have access to sufficient and nutritious food throughout the year and Goal 2.2: Eradication of all forms of malnutrition, including international goals for reducing stunting and wasting in children under five.

Alleviating Financial Burden relevant to SDG 1: No Poverty especially focus on Goal 1.3: Establish nationally appropriate social protection systems and measures for all, including minimum standards.

Empowering Women connected to SDG 5: Gender Equality especially emphasize on Goal 5.5: Ensure that women have equal opportunities for leadership and full participation in decision-making processes across political, economic, and public sectors.

Enhancing Healthcare Utilization connected to SDG 3: Good Health and Well-Being especially prioritized on Goal 3.8: Achieve universal health coverage, including financial risk protection and access to quality essential health services, as well as safe and affordable essential medicines and vaccines.

6. Recommendations and Conclusion

The recommendations outlined by the respondents emphasize several key measures to enhance the overall effectiveness and accessibility of the maternity allowance program. A significant focus is placed on simplifying the application process by reducing paperwork and increasing local support, making it easier for mothers to apply. There is also a strong call for raising public awareness about the program through mass media, community meetings, and social media, ensuring more mothers are informed about their eligibility. Additionally, many respondents suggested increasing the allowance amount to account for inflation and rising living costs. Reducing the number of required documents and allowing digital submissions could further streamline the process. Furthermore, there is a recognized need for additional assistance, such as healthcare, nutritional support, and childcare services, to complement the financial aid. Mothers are also encouraged to apply early and seek guidance from local authorities. Continuous monitoring and evaluation of the program's impact were suggested as crucial to adapting and improving outcomes over time. Implementing these recommendations could lead to a more inclusive, supportive, and responsive maternity allowance system.

To conclude the study on the impact of maternity allowance on maternal health revealed that the program has had a generally positive but uneven effect on the women who participated. The allowance alleviated some of the financial burden of maternity care, enabling women to seek medical attention more consistently and without delay. Despite these positive outcomes, challenges persist. It encountered difficulties in accessing the allowance, stemming from bureaucratic obstacles, limited awareness of the program, and logistical challenges, particularly in remote areas. These issues have hindered the program's ability to fully enhance maternal health outcomes across all regions. This variation underscores the need for more targeted approaches, such as increasing awareness efforts and simplifying the application process, to ensure that all eligible women can benefit from the program. Although the maternity allowance scheme has proven to be a valuable initiative for improving maternal health in rural areas, there is room for improvement. Enhancing program accessibility and raising awareness will be essential to maximizing its effectiveness and ensuring it addresses the health needs of all mothers in the area.

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